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HOW TO STIMULATE COLLABORATION AND PERFORMANCE OF HIGHLY DIVERSE STUDENT TEAMS IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION?

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Due to technical changes and globalized markets, work is increasingly organized in teams consisting of people with different disciplinary and cultural backgrounds. Diversity in teams, especially deep-level diversity (attitudinal diversity, such as variations in values, attitudes, personality etc. (Harrison, Price, & Bell, 1998)), might stimulate innovation, because different perspectives and expertise can be used to solve problems. Diversity, however, may also lead to miscommunication and conflicts between team members (van Veelen & Ufkes, 2019). In engineering education, new educational formats such as challenge-based learning result in educational designs in which students with various backgrounds and expertise are required to collaborate together on projects and assignments (Kohn Rådberg, Lundqvist, Malmqvist, & Hagvall Svensson, 2020). But what is the best way to compose these teams and to support these teams in order to maximize the potential of these diverse teams and minimize possible negative effects?

In this workshop we present the materials and outcomes of a deep-level diversity intervention which was tested among 1100 engineering students from different disciplines and culture while they participated in a challenge-based international project week. During the project week, students worked in teams on different company assignments. On the first day, half of the student teams participated in the intervention. The intervention was designed to increase awareness of each other's professional identity (who are you as a professional?) in order to lower inter-group bias and stimulate the development of a team identity (Van Knippenberg, De Dreu, & Homan, 2004). They received feedback on their professional identity (competencies, values, interests and personality) and were challenged to design a team plan while taking into account each other's unique talents. We compared the project results, quality of collaboration, and feeling of inclusiveness of these teams that participated in the intervention with the student teams that did not participate. We will start the workshop with introducing the concept of professional identity and how we conceptualise this in our project Bridge the gap! (Endedijk, van Veelen, & Möwes, 2017) and giving the participants the opportunity to do a short self-test to find out about their own professional identity. We will show the materials and set-up of the intervention, followed by an online voting to ask the participants to predict the outcomes of our study. This will provide insights in our own pre-conceptions of benefits and costs of diversity in teamwork in engineering education. After that, the outcomes of our intervention study will be shared via infographics. We will show how diversity (objective and perceived) in teams in terms of field of study, experience, national background and gender affected the quality of collaboration, performance and feelings of belonging and to what extent the intervention helped to counteract negative effects and further stimulate positive effects. The participants are invited to engage in small groups in a quick design of a similar intervention for their own

courses that require collaboration in diverse teams. The workshop will end with lessons learned: what to do and what to avoid when designing projects for teams with members with a diverse background.

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